

Biostimulant effect of a novel seawater-adapted strain of *Scenedesmus almeriensis* on garden geranium

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Abstract

Microalgae production requires substantial water resources. For this reason, different strategies are being investigated such as cultivating microalgae using wastewater or seawater. The goal of this study was to demonstrate the biostimulant effect of *Scenedesmus almeriensis* produced using both freshwater and seawater. This is the first time that the biostimulant capacity of seawater-produced *Scenedesmus almeriensis* has been investigated. The biostimulant capacity of the biomass was assessed *in vitro* using different bioassays and validated *in vivo* using *Pelargonium × hortorum*, commonly called zonal geranium or garden geranium. The *in vitro* results showed that *S. almeriensis* extracts significantly improved the germination index (GI) in cress seeds and stimulated root formation in soybean seedlings compared to the water control. The *in vivo* trials confirmed that plants treated with *S. almeriensis* extracts experienced significant increases in the height, number of leaves and flowers, and dry weight of various organs, indicating an overall improvement in plant biomass and structural health. The results also revealed that the biomass produced in freshwater was more effective than that obtained in seawater, probably due to a lower accumulation of saline compounds that can reduce the biostimulant activity.

Keywords: Agriculture, biomass, geranium, ornamental plants, microalgae, sustainability.

1. Introduction

Ornamental plant production is one of the most diverse and dynamic agricultural sectors in the world. The European Union is ranked first in the sales of potted ornamental plants, having 31% of the global market, followed by China and the United States in second and third place with 18.6 and 12.5%, respectively [1]. It is an important industrial sector; in 2021, the value of the annual flower trade amounted to 5.6 billion euros [2]. The increasing demand for ornamental plants requires sensible and environmentally sustainable production. This, in turn, requires strategies such as integrated nutrient management, the use of recycled materials and the development of new species that adapt to changing climatic conditions [3]. Other strategies such as the use of plant biostimulants and biopesticides derived from renewable resources are also being investigated as approaches to increase the sustainability of ornamental plant production.

Plant biostimulants significantly enhance growth by, for example, improving water uptake or stimulating root and shoot development [4]. One of the most widely investigated plant biostimulants are microalgae [5]. These microorganisms can also serve as biological control agents or biopesticides, promoting healthy growth and improving soil fertility [6]. They are unicellular photosynthetic organisms that can capture carbon dioxide and convert it into a biomass rich in micro and macronutrients, including a variety of bioactive compounds such as phytohormones, polyphenols, and carotenoids [7]. Several challenges still exist regarding the sustainable production of microalgae due to factors such as their high water requirements. Different strategies are currently being implemented to reduce freshwater consumption; these include producing microalgae in wastewater or seawater and reusing the culture medium [8,9]. Using wastewater

for microalgae production is a promising approach, as microalgae can metabolise the nitrogen and phosphorus present in the wastewater into valuable compounds [10,11]. Similarly, cultivating microalgae with seawater saves on freshwater and simultaneously reduces production costs. Using seawater has the added advantage of reducing the risk of contamination with fungi and bacteria [12]. Finally, the reuse of the exhausted culture medium is also being investigated because this strategy can reduce freshwater use by 84% and reduce nutrient use by 55% [13].

Among the genera being studied as plant biostimulants are *Dunaliella*, *Isochrysis*, *Nannochloropsis*, *Scenedesmus*, *Arthrospira*, and *Chlorella*. Various research studies have been conducted in which their biomass has been applied in different ways. For example, Mutale-Joan et al. [14] carried out a study in which extracts of *Aphanothece sp.* and *Chlorella ellipsoidea* were applied to tomato plants at a concentration of 0.1, 0.5 or 1.0 g·L⁻¹. The treated plants presented an increase in root length and shoots, as well as a greater increase in dry weight and maximum nutrient absorption. Another study carried out on lettuce plants showed that the application of *Scenedesmus quadricuada* positively affected seedling growth, acting at the level of the shoots [4]. These strains are commonly produced using freshwater. The type of water used to produce microalgae has a striking effect on their biomass composition and bioactivity [15]. The effect of wastewater on the biostimulant potential of several microalgae has been investigated [16,17]. Similarly, some seawater strains, such as *Nannochloropsis gaditana* [18], have been studied but most of the biostimulant extracts evaluated to date were obtained from biomass produced in freshwater.

Scenedesmus almeriensis is a freshwater strain that stands out for its robustness and rapid growth, which allows the efficient production of high-quality biomass [19]. The effect of seawater on the biostimulant capacity of this microalga has not yet been investigated, nor has the effect of adapting freshwater strains to seawater on their biostimulant capacity. Adapting freshwater strains to seawater is of interest because seawater constitutes approximately 97% of all the water available on the planet [20]. For this reason, the objective of this work was to evaluate the biostimulant capacity of *Scenedesmus almeriensis* grown in both seawater and freshwater, and to validate the effectiveness of this microalga as a biostimulant using *Pelargonium × hortorum* var. *Silvia*.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Microalgae production

The microalga studied was *Scenedesmus almeriensis* (CCAP 276/24). This strain can be produced outdoors in Almeria (Spain) throughout the year using either freshwater [21] or wastewater [22]. It has recently been adapted to seawater in the laboratory (data pending publication). Briefly, the adaptation of the strain was carried out using 250 mL bubble columns with pH, temperature, and illumination control. The sea salt concentration was gradually increased from 0 to 35 g·L⁻¹ over a period of approximately 3 months. A metagenomic analysis was conducted to ensure that both cultures (freshwater and seawater) were *Scenedesmus* sp. In this study, the biomass was produced indoors using artificially illuminated 10 L controlled bubble columns. The culture medium used was a commercial fertiliser mixture with a composition of 0.90 g·L⁻¹ NaNO₃, 0.18 g·L⁻¹ MgSO₄, 0.14 g·L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄ and 0.03 g·L⁻¹ Karentol (Konegard, Barcelona, Spain). The latter is a

mixture of micronutrient that includes B, Cu, Fe, Mn, Mo, and Zn. The culture medium was prepared using either tap water or seawater. The biomass was harvested by centrifugation, frozen, freeze-dried, and stored at -20 °C until further use. The nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium content of the biomass was 5.51 ± 0.26 , 0.32 ± 0.08 , and 0.63 ± 0.05 % on a dry weight basis, respectively. These values were determined by ICP-MS, as described in a previous study [23].

2.2 Preparation of the biostimulant extract

The freeze-dried biomass was resuspended in water at a concentration of 100 g·L⁻¹, stirred at 150 rpm for 10 min and sonicated using a SONOPLUS HD4200 ultrasonic homogeniser (Bandelin electronic GmbH, Berlin, Germany) operating at 20 kHz and 200 W. The suspension volume was 500 mL and the sonication was applied for 20 min, controlling the temperature below 35 °C. The disrupted biomass was then stored at -20 °C until further use.

2.3 Assessment of biostimulant activity *in vitro*

2.3.1 Germination index of watercress seeds (*Lepidium sativum* L.)

To determine the germination index (*GI*), the microalgal extracts were prepared at a concentration of 0.1 or 0.5 g·L⁻¹. The *GI* was determined following a previously described methodology [24]. The results were compared to a negative control, which was distilled water, and a positive control, which was gibberellic acid at a concentration of 1 mg·L⁻¹. The *GI* was determined using 25 commercial watercress seeds (*Lepidium sativum* L.) placed in Petri dishes containing a Whatman No. 5 filter paper. The test was carried out in triplicate, using a total of 75 seeds per treatment. Once the seeds were placed in the Petri dishes, 2 mL of

each treatment were added. The seeds were then incubated for 3 days at 24 °C in the dark. The *GI* was determined using the following equation:

$$GI(\%) = \frac{N \cdot L}{N_c \cdot L_c} \cdot 100$$

where *N* is the number of germinated seeds, *L* is the average length of the germinated seeds, *N_c* is the number of germinated seeds treated with distilled water, and *L_c* refers to the average length of the germinated seeds when treated with distilled water alone.

2.3.2 Adventitious root induction of soybeans (*Glycine max L.*)

The root formation capacity of the extracts was determined following a previously described methodology [24]. Commercial soybeans (*Glycine max L.*) were purchased from a commercial retailer. The seeds were planted at a depth of 1 cm in moistened perlite bedded in plastic trays. The trays were placed in an incubation chamber for 7 days, maintaining a 12:12 h light/dark cycle at a temperature of 27 °C. Subsequently, 3 seedlings were cut 3 cm below the cotyledon and placed in vials containing 20 mL of either distilled water (the negative control), indole-3-butyric acid at 1 mg·L⁻¹ (the positive control), or the microalgal extracts at concentrations of 0.5 or 2.0 g·L⁻¹. The seedlings were incubated for 7 days, adding distilled water as necessary to compensate for evaporation. Finally, the number of roots greater than 1 mm was counted in each hypocotyl. Each treatment was assessed in triplicate.

2.4 Assessment of biostimulant activity *in vivo*

2.4.1 Experimental procedure

The validation of the biostimulant effects was carried out in a 170 m² greenhouse located in the agricultural experimental area of the University of Almeria in Spain (36°49'38"N 2°24'20"W). The greenhouse has a centralised ventilation system designed to activate its extractor fan when the temperature inside the greenhouse rises above 25 °C. To monitor the environmental conditions inside the facility, a portable PCE-HT 114 data logger (PCE Instruments, Albacete, Spain) was used. This was placed at a height of 1.30 m.

The *Pelargonium × hortorum* var. Silvia plants were obtained from the company Plantas de Andalucía (Almeria, Spain). The transplantation was carried out in 1.5 L pots using a substrate composed exclusively of coconut fibre, as described elsewhere [25]. The plants were manually watered every two days. The amount of water was adjusted according to the needs of the plants and the climatic conditions, ensuring that 20% of the water applied was drained. On average, each plant received 110 mL of water per day. The microalgae application was carried out weekly. Two strategies were followed: 50 mL of the microalgal extract were applied directly to the substrate and 10 mL were applied to the leaf surface by spraying (foliar application). The concentrations studied were 0.1, 0.5, and 1.0 g·L⁻¹. For the control, the same procedure was followed, but water was applied instead of the microalgal extract.

The experimental design was carried out in a completely randomised fashion, with 8 treatments of 8 replicates each, a total of 64 experimental units. The treatments tested were as follows: T1: irrigation water; T2: water with nutrient solution; T3: *Scenedesmus almeriensis* produced using freshwater at a concentration of 0.1 g·L⁻¹; T4: *Scenedesmus almeriensis* produced using freshwater at a concentration of 0.5 g·L⁻¹; T5 *Scenedesmus almeriensis* produced

using freshwater at a concentration of 1.0 g·L⁻¹, T6: *Scenedesmus almeriensis* produced using seawater at a concentration of 0.1 g·L⁻¹, T7: *Scenedesmus almeriensis* produced using seawater at a concentration of 0.5 g·L⁻¹; and T8 *Scenedesmus almeriensis* produced using seawater at a concentration of 1.0 g·L⁻¹. The nutrient solution concentrations were prepared from a 100 g·L⁻¹ stock solution. To obtain the concentrations of 0.1, 0.5, and 1.0 g·L⁻¹, the following dilutions were made: for the 0.1 g·L⁻¹ concentration, 0.6 mL of stock solution was used; for the 0.5 g·L⁻¹ concentration, 3 mL of stock solution was used; and for the 1 g·L⁻¹ concentration, 6 mL of stock solution was used. A 20L nutrient solution was prepared containing 2.55 mL·L⁻¹ HNO₃, 10.0 g·L⁻¹ Ca(NO₃)₂, 8.6 g·L⁻¹ KNO₃, 2.3 g·L⁻¹ NH₄NO₃, 1.8 g·L⁻¹ K₂SO₄, and 5.4 g·L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄. An analysis of the solution showed the following anion and cation concentrations: 203.39 mg·L⁻¹ PO₄³⁻, 172.39 mg·L⁻¹ SO₄²⁻, 585.39 mg·L⁻¹ NO₃⁻, 53.90 mg·L⁻¹ NH₄⁺, 208,22 mg·L⁻¹ K⁺, 24.36 mg·L⁻¹ Mg²⁺, 123.17 mg·L⁻¹ Ca²⁺, 134.02 mg·L⁻¹ Na⁺, and 271.78 mg·L⁻¹ Cl⁻.

2.4.2 Plant parameters

The plants were analysed 70 days after transplantation. The following parameters were measured: plant height, plant diameter, number of leaves, leaf size, and number of flowers. The height of the plant was measured from its base to the tip of the apex using a flexible ruler. The diameter of the plant was calculated as the average value of two diameters measured perpendicularly. The leaf area was calculated via a non-destructive method using the equation:

$$S = a + bLW$$

where S is leaf area, L is the length of the leaf (cm), W is the width of the leaf, and the coefficients a (0.07) and b (0.65) are specific for *Pelargonium x hortorum* [26].

The plants were dismantled and their organs separated into leaves, stems, roots, and flowers. All the samples were washed and dried with filter paper so that their individual fresh and dry weights could be determined. To calculate the dry weight, the organs were placed in filter-paper envelopes and dried in a EFN500 oven (Nüve, Ankara, Turkey) at 60 °C for 48 h [25].

2.5 Statistical analysis

A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to identify significant differences. A Fisher's least significant difference test ($p < 0.05$) was performed to determine which treatments were significantly different from each other. These analyses were performed using Statgraphics 19[®] Centurion software (Statgraphics Technologies, VA, USA).

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Biostimulant effects *in vitro*

The microalga *Scenedesmus almeriensis* was selected based on previous studies demonstrating its efficacy as a biostimulant, promoting plant growth due to the presence of compounds with cytokinin and auxin-like effects [27]. However, the biostimulant effect of a given biomass depends mainly on its composition, which is affected by environmental and operational conditions during its production. For example, it is known that the protein content of microalgae grown in a culture medium with no nitrogen limitation is maximal during the exponential growth phase [28], and microalgae-derived proteins have proven biostimulant

effects [29]. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the effect of salinity on the biostimulant capacity of *Scenedesmus almeriensis* has not yet been evaluated. Indeed, this is the first report related to this microalga produced using seawater. Figure 1 shows the biostimulant capacity of the microalgal extracts. The GI of the seeds, shown in Figure 1A, is important because it is a quantitative determination of seed health and viability. It provides a quantitative measure of the capacity and speed at which a batch of seeds can germinate under specific conditions [30]. Gibberellins are a group of plant hormones that play an important role in the initiation of seed germination and stem elongation [31,32]. They are key to breaking seed dormancy and promoting cell elongation, which facilitates rapid and vigorous germination [33]. The results obtained show that microalgae can positively influence germination, suggesting the extracts have a similar effect to that of gibberellins. This bioactivity was greatest at the highest biomass concentration ($p < 0.05$) and when the biomass was produced using seawater ($p < 0.05$). It is known that the use of different types of water can significantly affect the composition of microalgal biomass [34]. It is likely that the use of seawater prompted the production of biostimulant compounds, probably in response to salinity stress. It is also known that gibberellin levels in plants are triggered as a defence against biotic stress caused by, for example, reactive oxygen species, cold, or salt [35]. It is likely that salinity triggered the production and accumulation of gibberellin-like compounds, as happens in plants. A previous study demonstrated that the concentration of biostimulant compounds, such as succinic acid, was higher in the biomass of *Arthrospira platensis* produced using seawater compared to the same strain produced using freshwater [23]. In addition, the use of seawater during biomass production could have enriched the content of

essential minerals, which, in turn, could favour seedling growth and development [36]. The results reported in this study are in line with those published in previous studies. For example, in a study carried out by Navarro-López et al. [24], the GI of watercress (*Lepidium sativum*) seeds treated with *Scenedesmus* at a concentration of $0.5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ was evaluated. In that study, the biomass was produced using freshwater or pig slurry. The results revealed a 100% increase in GI compared to the control treatment (water alone), suggesting that the application of *Scenedesmus* at this concentration can significantly promote seed germination. Overall, the results revealed, for the first time, that the stress caused by seawater on the cells of *Scenedesmus almeriensis* can trigger the production and accumulation of gibberellin-like compounds that promote seed germination. The biostimulant effect was shown to be strain- and concentration-dependent ($p < 0.05$).

Root initiation and elongation are significantly influenced by auxins [37]. There is a direct relationship between auxin concentration and the number of roots formed [38]. The auxin levels are crucial for improving their efficiency in plants. Their concentration and type, influenced by both external and internal factors, play a key role in adventitious root formation [39]. Figure 1B shows the effect of the microalgal extracts on root formation. Overall, both samples led to a significant improvement ($p < 0.05$). Freshwater microalgae proved more effective at root formation, suggesting that the cultivation conditions and the environment in which the microalgae grow may influence their chemical composition and thus their ability to act as biostimulants [40]. The root formation improvement was ~50% higher when the biomass was produced using freshwater compared to using seawater. The presence of salt in the biomass produced using seawater might

also have contributed to the lower biostimulant effect given that sodium chloride causes osmotic stress that adversely influences root growth, including a reduction in root meristem size as well as growth inhibition [41]. However, in both cases, the rooting capacity of the microalgal extract outperformed that of the water treatment by over 300% ($p < 0.05$). In a study carried out by Ruales et al. [30], a significant increase in root size was observed when applying a $2 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ treatment containing a microalga of the genus *Scenedesmus*. In that study, the use of the microalgal extract led to a 156% increase in root growth compared to the control treatment. This remarkable increase in root biomass suggests that using microalgae such as *Scenedesmus* can be an effective strategy for improving nutrient uptake efficiency in plants, and thus avoiding leachate contamination. By promoting root growth and function, microalgae can enhance nutrient uptake and simultaneously reduce the excess nutrients remaining in the soil, lowering the risk of nutrients being leached into groundwater, although this would need to be assessed *in vivo* in future studies.

3.2 *In vivo* assessment of biostimulant effects

Biostimulants are products that can promote the growth and development of various crops, under either favourable or stressful conditions [42]. They can be applied as foliar or soil sprays depending on their composition and expected results [43]. Foliar application is more common in the literature and previous studies have suggested that the foliar application of microalgae (*Chlorella vulgaris*) might lead to greater biostimulant effects than soil drench [44]. However, other studies observed improved plant characteristics, such as in the chlorophyll content, after the soil application of plant growth promoting bacteria compared to foliar application [45]. For this reason, in our study, the microalgae

extracts were applied in both ways. Future studies will aim to optimise the dosage and application strategy. Plant height is an important agronomic trait that is closely associated with crop yield and quality. The effect of applying microalgae on the height of the plants is shown in Figure 2A. Overall, significant differences were found between the various treatments ($p < 0.05$). The tallest plants were obtained when applying the nutrient solution (NS), reaching an average height of 19.8 cm. Applying microalgae also led to increased height ($p < 0.05$). Gibberellins play a key role in regulating plant height [46]; therefore, the results observed *in vivo* support those presented above in the *in vitro* trials. In this work, a dose-dependent effect was observed with taller plants being obtained using higher microalgae concentrations in the extract ($p < 0.05$). The effect was especially noticeable when using the biomass produced using freshwater ($p < 0.05$). No effect on plant height was observed when using extracts at a concentration of $0.1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, demonstrating how important it is to optimize the dosage. The height of the plants when treated with microalgae at a concentration of $0.1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ was on average 8.1 cm. Microalgae can supply essential nutrients and bioactive compounds that mimic the action of plant hormones, such as the above-mentioned gibberellins, auxins, or cytokinins, stimulating cell division and elongation, both processes being crucial for growth [47]. For example, it has been found that polysaccharides increase the length of tomato and pepper plants by 20 and 30%, respectively [48].

Another important parameter for zonal geranium plants is their diameter. The diameter is an important indicator of the plant's general health and carrying capacity. It is also an important parameter for evaluating the quality of ornamental plants and contributes to consumer expectations [49]. The results, shown in

Figure 2B, reveal that the use of microalgae, even at the lowest concentration studied, had a positive effect on the diameter of the plants ($p < 0.05$), with the microalgal extracts showing a dose-dependent effect, leading to a 15.4, 18.4, or 26.9% increase when the microalgae were applied at a concentration of 0.1, 0.5, or 1.0 g·L⁻¹, respectively. The results observed in this work are in line with those of previous studies. For example, a previous study observed that the foliar application of another microalga (*Chlorella vulgaris*) could increase the diameter of zonal geranium plants from 18 to over 20 cm [50].

Leaves and flowers are especially important in ornamental plants. The effect of the microalgae on the number of leaves is shown in Figure 3A. The results demonstrated that both biomasses had a positive effect on the number of leaves per plant ($p < 0.05$). In addition, a dose-dependent effect was observed, with the highest number of leaves occurring at the highest biomass concentration studied ($p < 0.05$). The application of *Scenedesmus almeriensis* extracts produced using freshwater led to a 16.2, 47.9, or 70.6% increase when the microalgae were applied at a concentration of 0.1, 0.5, or 1.0 g·L⁻¹, respectively. When produced using seawater, the extracts increased the number of leaves by 17.6, 25.9, and 31.7 at concentrations of 0.1, 0.5, or 1.0 g·L⁻¹, respectively. In addition, the biomass produced using freshwater showed a higher biostimulant effect than the biomass produced using seawater ($p < 0.05$). This can be attributed, as suggested before, to a lower accumulation of biostimulant compounds. The number of leaves is important for plants as it may affect stomatal conductance and the rate of photosynthetic induction [51]. Microalgae can supply nutrients and plant hormones that promote the formation of new leaves, thus improving photosynthetic efficiency [52]. In a previous work carried out on strawberries, the

application of *Scenedesmus* biomass increased the number of leaves by 16% [53], which is comparable to the results obtained in this work. In addition, this is the first time that the biostimulant effect of a seawater-adapted *Scenedesmus* strain has been validated in a field trial. More leaves ensure that the plant captures more light energy. Other parameters such as leaf health, orientation, or chlorophyll content are also critical to photosynthesis although these were not determined in the present study. The size of the leaf surface is likewise important. The leaf area, which is closely related to the number of leaves and the diameter of the plant, was greater at the highest biomass concentration studied. The best performing treatments were the biomass produced using seawater at a concentration of $1.0 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (165.5 cm^2) and the biomass produced using freshwater at a concentration of $1.0 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (165.4 cm^2). Microalgae at concentrations of $1.0 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ are effective at maximising leaf area, which is critical for energy production and the uptake of nutrients [54]. The results are in line with other studies. For example, in a previous work, the authors observed increases in both the nutrient concentration and the chlorophyll content of strawberry plants treated with microalgae, which resulted in an increased leaf area [55].

Flowers are also key in ornamental plants. The number of flowers on each plant is shown in Figure 3B. Overall, the greatest number of flowers was obtained with the microalgae produced using freshwater ($p < 0.05$). Surprisingly, the number of flowers per plant was exceptionally high when applying *Scenedesmus* produced using freshwater ($p < 0.05$), increasing from 6.4 to 10.4, 11.9, and 12.4 when applying the extract of *Scenedesmus almeriensis* produced using freshwater at a concentration of 0.1, 0.5, or $1.0 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, respectively. No differences were observed between the NS and this extract at concentrations of 0.5 or $1.0 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$.

When produced using seawater, the number of flowers was higher than that of water alone only at the highest biomass concentration tested ($p < 0.05$). In this case, the number of flowers increased from 6.4 to 9.3 ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, in a previous study carried out on *Petunia × hybrida*, using microalgae led to 16% more flowers compared to the control [56]. This may be because of the presence of hormonal compounds and nutrients in *Scenedesmus* that promote flower formation [57]. However, it is likely that the stress suffered by the microalgal cells due to seawater salinity affected the production and accumulation of these biostimulant compounds. For example, the number of amino acids with proven biostimulant effects was lower in *Arthrospira platensis* biomass produced using seawater than that produced using freshwater [23].

Figure 4 shows the effect of microalgae on the dry weight of the leaves, flowers, roots, and stems. The dry weight of the leaves is shown in Figure 4A. Overall, the NS, used as a positive control, gave the highest results ($p < 0.05$). This was to be expected, as the plants were provided with an excess of nutrients that allowed them to grow under optimal conditions. In this case, the dry weight of the leaves per plant was 1.5 kg. The application of microalgae resulted in a significant increase in leaf dry weight compared to the application of water alone, especially when the microalgae were produced using freshwater ($p < 0.05$). In addition, it was observed that higher biomass concentrations were directly related to greater leaf dry weight. The dry weight of the leaves increased from 0.55 kg (water) to 0.65, 0.82, or 1.12 kg when the freshwater-produced biomass was applied at a concentration of 0.1, 0.5, or 1.0 g·L⁻¹, respectively. Despite the observed increase, the dry weight of the leaves was lower than that of the NS, even at the highest concentration studied. Leaf dry weight is a key indicator of leaf biomass

and is closely linked to both leaf number and leaf size. Larger leaves are beneficial as they increase the photosynthetic capacity of the plant, thus improving its overall performance and efficiency in capturing light for photosynthesis [58]. In addition, Figure 4B shows the dry weight of the flowers. The NS (0.29 kg) led to a greater dry weight of flowers compared to water (0.20 kg) ($p < 0.05$). In this case, the plants treated with microalgae showed surprisingly high values, especially when the microalgal biomass was produced using freshwater ($p < 0.05$). When produced with freshwater, the dry weight of the flowers per plant was 0.32, 0.36, or 0.39 kg applied at a concentration of 0.1, 0.5, or 1.0 g·L⁻¹, respectively. When produced using seawater, the dry weight of flowers per plant was also higher than the control, weighing 0.22, 0.19, or 0.23 g·L⁻¹ at a concentration of 0.1, 0.5, or 1.0 g·L⁻¹, respectively. In both cases, the dry weight of the flowers was higher than that of the positive control ($p < 0.05$), which suggests that the biomass contained compounds that triggered the production of flowers despite being produced under suboptimal conditions. These results are in line with those reported above, bearing in mind that the dry weight of the flowers is closely related to the number of flowers and their size. A greater dry weight indicates a greater flower biomass, which can translate into a higher plant yield. By promoting the formation of more and larger flowers, microalgae contribute to increased biomass and therefore plant productivity. This parameter is also a positive indicator of photosynthetic efficiency. Similar results have been observed elsewhere using other microalgae. For example, it was found that a foliar application of microalgae led to a 20% increase in the flower dry weight compared to the control, namely irrigation using just water [56]. Moreover, Figure 4C shows the effect of microalgae use on the dry weight of the roots. When using

water alone, the dry weight of the roots was 0.48 kg per plant. Overall, both biomasses promoted root development when used at concentrations higher than 0.5 g·L⁻¹ ($p < 0.05$). The dry weight of the roots per plant increased to 0.52 or 0.56 kg when applying *Scenedesmus almeriensis* biomass at a concentration of 0.5 or 1.0 g·L⁻¹, respectively. These results are in line with those shown in Figure 1, since both biomasses were able to promote root development *in vitro*. No major differences were observed between the biomass produced using freshwater or seawater. The roots were bigger than when using the NS ($p < 0.05$), which can be attributed to the much higher nutrient availability with this treatment (no need for large roots). The results highlight the capacity of *Scenedesmus almeriensis* to stimulate root development and growth. The same effect was previously observed when applying a microalgal extract to tomato at a concentration of 1 g·L⁻¹, obtaining a greater root dry weight [59]. Greater root dry weight suggests a better nutrient and water uptake capacity, which may result in healthier and more vigorous growth. The increase in root size is due to the fact that greater root growth increases the surface area in contact with the soil, which directly improves the accessibility and uptake of nutrients [14]. This allows a more efficient use of nutrients and simultaneously reduces contamination by leaching.

Finally, Figure 4D shows the effect of microalgae on the stem dry weight. The results suggest that *Scenedesmus almeriensis* produced using freshwater had a positive effect ($p < 0.05$). This did not happen when the biomass produced using seawater was used. A dose-dependent effect was observed, with the greatest dry weight occurring when the most concentrated extract was used ($p < 0.05$). Overall, the 1.0 g·L⁻¹ and 0.5 g·L⁻¹ treatments showed the best results. The stem dry weight reflects the accumulation of biomass and the robustness of the tissue,

which are crucial for structural support and nutrient conduction. The effectiveness of freshwater treatments suggests that salinity could negatively affect biomass accumulation in this organ, highlighting the importance of the type of culture medium on the efficacy of the microalgal treatments.

Conclusions

Aqueous extracts of *Scenedesmus almeriensis* have been shown to have a significant biostimulant effect both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. The extracts were able to improve several plant growth parameters, such as seed germination, root formation, and leaf and flower development. These positive effects can be attributed to the presence of phytohormones such as gibberellins and auxins. The *in vivo* tests revealed that *Scenedesmus almeriensis* extracts significantly increased the plant height, the number of leaves and flowers, and the dry weight of different organs, indicating an overall improvement in plant biomass and structural health. The present study aimed to assess the biostimulant effect of *Scenedesmus almeriensis* produced using seawater. The efficacy of the *Scenedesmus almeriensis* extracts was higher when the biomass was produced in freshwater rather than in seawater. This was probably due to a lower accumulation of phytohormones caused by the stress suffered from the medium's high salinity. This difference highlights the importance of the culture medium's composition when producing agricultural products such as plant biostimulants. Future works will optimise the dosage and identify which compounds are responsible for the bioactivities observed.

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Declaration of interests

The authors have no conflict of interests to declare.

Author contributions: CRediT

Rivera-Sánchez, E.: Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – original drafts; Villaró-Cos, S.: Investigation; Jiménez-Becker, S.: Conceptualization, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing; Rapalo-Cruz, A.: Investigation; Lafarga, T.: Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

Figure legends

Figure 1. (A) Germination index and (B) adventitious root formation. The results are expressed as a percentage of variation compared to distilled water and are expressed as mean values \pm SD. FW and SW stand for freshwater and seawater, respectively.

Figure 2. Effect of the microalgae on (A) plant height and (B) plant diameter. The results are expressed as mean values \pm SD. NS, FW, and SW stand for nutrient solution, freshwater and seawater, respectively.

Figure 3. Effect of the microalgae on (A) the number of leaves per plant and (B) the number of flowers per plant. The results are expressed as mean values \pm SD. NS, FW, and SW stand for nutrient solution, freshwater and seawater, respectively.

Figure 4. Effect of the microalgae on the dry weight of the (A) leaves, (B) flowers, (C) roots, and (D) stems. The results are expressed as mean values \pm SD. NS, FW, and SW stand for nutrient solution, freshwater and seawater, respectively.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

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